

was significant up to 90 kg N/ha (see table). The new Basmati varieties yielded significantly higher than Basmati 370. Kasturi and HKR228 produced almost similar yields (3.3-3.4 t/ha) that were significantly higher than that of Pusa Basmati 1 (3 t/ha). □

Aruna (MO 8), a high-yielding rice variety with seed dormancy and brown planthopper (BPH) resistance from Kerala, India

N. R. Bai, R. Devika, A. Regina, S. L. Kumary, D. S. Radhadevi, and C. A. Joseph, Rice Research Station (RRS), Moncompu, India

Kuttanad is a unique delta region in Kerala, with 52,000 ha of riceland 0.5-2 m below sea level. Wet season rice harvest coincides with the monsoon. Rice grains often germinate within the panicle. Pests, especially BPH, are endemic because of the warm, humid climate. Many popular high-yielding varieties have neither BPH resistance nor seed dormancy.

Aruna (MO 8)—culture KAU93 derived from Jaya/Ptb 33—was released in 1990. It has red-kerneled, medium-bold grains and 1-mo seed dormancy. The short-duration (110 d) dwarf rice is also resistant to BPH.

In field trials 1983-84, Aruna (MO 8) consistently outyielded local checks (Table 1). It also showed resistance to many pests (Table 2). □

Table 1. MO 8 (Aruna) yields in Kerala, India.

Trial	Grain yield (t/ha)	
	MO 8	Check variety ^a
Rice research station, Moncompu, 1983-84, 3 seasons	5.3	4.9
Multilocation trials, 1984 wet season	5.2	4.4
All India Coordinated trials PVT-2, 1984 wet season, 8 locations	3.4	2.9
PVT-2, 1985 dry season, 6 locations	3.8	2.5
Farm trials, 1987-89, 3 seasons	4.3	3.6

^aJyothi for research station, multilocation, and farm trials and Rasi for PVT-2.

Table 2. MO 8 reaction to pests at RRS Moncompu and in Hyderabad.^a

Variety	Score at RRS Moncompu							Score at DRR ^b , Hyderabad ^d
	Sheath blight ^c	Sheath rot ^c	Stem borer ^c	Leaf roller ^c	Gall midge ^c	BPH ^d	BPH	
KAU93	1.4	3.7	1.0	1.9	1.0	1.7	2.2	2.5
Jyothi	4.7	4.5	3.0	3.2	3.0	3.7	2.3	4.2

^a Scored by *Standard evaluation system for rice* (SES) on a scale of 0-9. ^b Directorate of Rice Research. ^c Field screening. ^d Seedling screening.

Zhe 8619, a promising rice with high yields and high ratooning ability in China

Jin Qingsheng, Qiu Boqin, and Lu Rubi, Crop Institute, Zhejiang Academy of Agricultural Sciences (ZAAS), Hangzhou 310021, China

Zhe 8619, a semidwarf indica variety derived from Milyang 56/4B-58 at ZAAS, is suitable for two seasons in the double-cropped area of southern China. In Zhejiang, Jiangxi, and Hubei, it performed well in 1988-90 adaptation and yield trials in early (ES) and late seasons (LS).

Average grain yield was 7.8 t/ha in

ES and 6.8 t/ha in LS. The highest yield of 11.2 t/ha was 10-15% higher than those of local check varieties. Average growth duration was 115-125 d in ES and 90-110 d in LS. In 1990, Zhe 8619 outyielded the hybrid rice check by 18.5% in ES and 4.3% in LS (Table 1).

Zhe 8619 is cold tolerant at the seedling stage and is resistant to blast and bacterial blight. No serious pests or diseases were observed in 1989-90. During the 1990 LS in Zhejiang and Jiangxi, bacterial blight attacked many rice varieties, but not Zhe 8619.

In 1990, the Zhe 8619 ratoon crop yield averaged 4 t/ha, 52% that of the main crop (7.7 t/ha). Ratoon crop duration was 56-61 d (Table 2). □

Table 1. Performance of Zhe 8619 in yield trials in Xiantao, Hubei, China, 1990.

Variety	Duration (d)	Yield (t/ha)	Increase over check (%)	Yield components				
				Panicles (no./m ²)	Spikelets (no./panicle)	Fertility (%)	1,000-grain wt (g)	Plant ht (cm)
<i>Early season</i>								
Zhe 8619	116	7.7	18.5	375	128	81.2	29.7	101
Chang-You 48-2 (check)	115	6.5	-	390	117	50.3	28.9	90
<i>Late season</i>								
Zhe 8619	91	7.2	4.3	290	112	79.2	29.5	95
Wei-You 49 (check)	96	6.9	-	269	114	69.9	29.1	89

Table 2. Ratoon rice yield and characteristics of Zhe 8619 in Xiantao, Hubei, China, 1990.^a

Stubble ht (cm)	Duration (d)	Plant ht (cm)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Spikelets (no./panicle)	Fertility (%)	1,000-grain wt (g)	Grain yield (t/ha)
15	61	72	238	83	65.3	28.6	3.9
25	58	73	254	75	77.0	29.1	4.1
30	56	65	330	77	60.6	29.5	4.3
40	56	72	259	68	79.0	29.7	4.0

^aPlot = 4 m² (2 × 2 m), 13- × 20-cm spacing.